

California Weedy Rice and Grasses Response to Glufosinate

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Introduction

- Weedy rice (*Oryza* spp.) is an important weed to cultivated rice.
- Five weedy rice accessions have been determined in California, all derived from wild, weedy, and cultivated rice parentage from within and outside California (1).
- There are no labeled herbicides for control of weedy rice in California.
- Barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), late watergrass (*Echinochloa oryzicola*), early watergrass (*Echinochloa oryzoides*), and sprangletop (*Leptochloa fascicularis*) are important weedy grasses and are difficult to control with current available herbicides because of herbicide-resistant populations.
- Glufosinate controls weeds by inhibiting glutamine synthase, an enzyme involved in the incorporation of ammonium into the amino acid glutamine (2).

Objective

- To determine the response of California weedy rice accessions and grasses to glufosinate herbicide.

Figure 1. Glufosinate dose-response on weedy rice accessions.

Materials and Methods

- Weedy rice accession 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and three rice varieties, M211, L207, and M206, were utilized.
- Barnyardgrass, late watergrass, early watergrass, and sprangletop were grass weed materials.
- Glufosinate application rates were 0, 61, 123, 246, 492, 984, 1968, and 3936 g ai ha⁻¹.
- The experiment was conducted on a randomized block design with 5 replications in the UC Davis greenhouse facilities.
- Dose-response curves based on the log-logistic model were used to determine the effective dose that provides 90% control (ED₉₀).
- The sprayer chamber was calibrated to deliver 187 L ha⁻¹ application volume at 275 kPa pressure. Observations were taken 28 DAT.

Figure 2: The effect of the glufosinate herbicide on rice at 28 days after treatment. Control, 1/16x, 1/8x, 1/4x, 1/2x, 1x, 2x, 4x, and 8x are equal to 0, 62, 123, 246, 492, 984, 1968, and 3936 g ai ha⁻¹, respectively. Top row from left to right is weedy rice accession 1, 2, and 3; bottom row from left to right is weedy rice accession 4, 5, and L207 rice variety.

Result and Discussion

- Glufosinate at 307, 381, 590 371, and 466 g ai ha⁻¹ caused 90% injury (ED₉₀) for weedy rice accessions 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively.
- Weedy rice accession 3 was the most tolerant, however, accession 1 was the most susceptible to glufosinate.
- ED₉₀ for the L207, M206, and M211 rice variety was observed at 373, 690, and 581 g ai ha⁻¹ glufosinate, respectively.
- ED₉₀ for barnyardgrass, late watergrass, early watergrass, and sprangletop was observed at 509, 458, 693, and 566 g ai ha⁻¹ glufosinate, respectively.
- Early watergrass was the most tolerant, and late watergrass was the most susceptible to glufosinate in tested grasses.

Figure 3. The effect of the glufosinate herbicide on weeds at 28 days after treatment. From left to right in each photo, control, 1/16x, 1/8x, 1/4x, 1/2x, 1x, 2x, 4x, and 8x are equal 0, 62, 123, 246, 492, 984, 1968, and 3936 g ai ha⁻¹ glufosinate, respectively. Top row from left to right is Barnyardgrass, late watergrass, and early watergrass; bottom row from left to right is the sprangletop, M206, and M211 rice variety

Table 1. Clethodim dose-response results and curves based on the log-logistic model to ED₅₀-ED₉₀

Order	Plants	ED50	ED90
1	Weedy Rice 1	180	307
2	Weedy Rice 2	197	381
3	Weedy Rice 3	326	590
4	Weedy Rice 4	285	371
5	Weedy Rice 5	308	466
6	Barnyardgrass (<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>)	212	509
7	Late watergrass (<i>Echinochloa oryzicola</i>)	306	458
8	Early watergrass (<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i>)	338	693
9	Sprangletop (<i>Leptochloa fascicularis</i>)	222	566
10	Rice (M211)	318	581
11	Rice (L207)	285	373
12	Rice (M206)	338	690

Conclusion

- Glufosinate effectively controlled weedy rice and grasses.
- Glufosinate is able to control between 307-693 gr ai ha⁻¹ and an average of 499 gr ai ha⁻¹ dose by 90% for both weedy rice and grasses.
- Early watergrass was determined as the most tolerant among the tested plants.
- These results indicated that glufosinate has great potential to be used as a spot treatment for the management of weedy rice and grass.

References

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